

Gravimetric Determination of Manganese(II) with N-Benzoyl-Phenylhydroxylamine

S. P. BAG and S. LAHIRI

Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-32

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N-Benzoyl-phenylhydroxylamine has been used to determine 5.0 to 28.0 mg of manganese(II) gravimetrically. The complex is precipitated quantitatively within the pH range, 6.3 to 7.8. The interference due to Mg^{2+} , As^{3+} , Sb^{3+} , MoO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} or La^{3+} has been avoided by using tartrate, cyanide, ammonium carbonate or ammonium acetate as the masking agents. The reagent has also been utilised for the separation of Mn^{2+} from Ti^{4+} , Fe^{3+} , Sn^{2+} , VO_3^- , Th^{4+} and Al^{3+} by adjustment of acidity. The precipitate is weighed as $Mn(C_{13}H_{10}O_2N)_2$ after drying at $110^\circ-120^\circ$. The accuracy is generally better than 0.3%.

AMONG the few organic reagents employed for gravimetric estimation of manganese (II) are tannin¹, anthranilic acid² and 8-hydroxyquinoline³. Manganese complex of tannin is not quantitatively precipitated and as with other metals, the precipitate must be ignited to oxide before weighing. The comparatively higher solubility of manganese anthranilate renders the acid only moderately useful as a precipitant. According to Neelakantam⁴, the determination of manganese (II) as oxinate³ cannot be recommended since the precipitate tends to decompose somewhat on drying. However, the oxine method has been later modified⁵ to satisfactory level. In this investigation, N-benzoyl-phenylhydroxylamine (N-BPHA), a ligand utilised in the gravimetric and/or spectrophotometric determination of various metal ions,^{6,7} has been found to be a promising one for gravimetric determination of manganese. The reagent reacts quantitatively with manganese (II) in the pH range 6.3 to 7.8, giving an insoluble metal complex. The faint yellow complex is thermally stable upto 241° and can be weighed as $Mn(C_{13}H_{10}O_2N)_2$ after drying at $110^\circ-120^\circ$. Interference due to a large number of ions has been removed by controlling the pH or using suitable masking agents.

Experimental

N-Benzoyl-phenylhydroxylamine: The reagent was prepared by the method as reported earlier^{6,8}. Reagent solutions were made by dissolving it in 10-20 ml of 90% ethanol before use.

Manganese (II) solution: A stock solution was prepared by dissolving manganese (II) chloride in 0.1M hydrochloric acid. The metal content was determined gravimetrically⁹.

Diverse ions: Solutions of other ions were prepared from the chloride or the nitrate salts of cations and from the sodium, potassium and ammonium

salts of anions. A few drops of a suitable acid was added to prevent hydrolysis where necessary.:

All chemicals used were reagent grade quality.

Apparatus: A Cambridge pH meter was used for pH measurements. Chevenard thermobalance (Type 3 Adamel, Paris) was used for thermogravimetry and a Sartorius semimicro single pan balance was employed for weighing.

Procedure: To an aliquot of standard solution containing 5.0 to 28.0 mg of manganese (II) was added 10 ml each of a 2% and a 20% solutions of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium potassium tartrate. It was diluted to 200 ml and the pH was adjusted at 6.5-7.5 with dilute solutions of sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid. The addition of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and tartrate were necessary to prevent oxidation and hydrolysis of the metal ions, respectively. The mixture was then heated to 40° and reagent (0.12-0.6 g) solution was added with stirring. The precipitate formed was digested on a hot water bath for 25 to 30 min. with occasional stirring. The precipitate was then collected on a weighed gooch crucible (no. 3), washed with hot water and dried at $110^\circ-120^\circ$ to constant weight. The metal content of the complex was obtained using a factor 0.1147. The results of one of several determinations of manganese with the reagent are given in Table 1.

Procedure in the presence of diverse ions: Solutions containing known amounts of manganese (II) and magnesium (II), arsenic (III), antimony (III), molybdenum (VI) or tungsten (VI) were mixed with tartrate (2.0 g) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.2 g) solutions and diluted to 200 ml. The pH of the mixture was adjusted between 6.3 and 6.6 and heated to 40° . Manganese (II) was then precipitated with N-BPHA and determined as described above.

However, 2.0 g of ammonium carbonate was added and the pH was adjusted between 6.3 and 6.6 to effect separation of manganese (II) from uranium (VI), while ammonium acetate (2.0 g) was used to mask lanthanum (III). For masking copper (II), nickel (II), cobalt (II), zinc (II), cadmium (II),

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF MANGANESE(II)

Mn taken (mg)	Wt. of complex (mg)	Mn found (mg)	Error (%)
5.22	45.5	5.21	-0.19
12.55	109.0	12.50	-0.39
19.30	168.7	19.34	+0.02
24.81	216.1	24.78	-0.12
28.16	246.5	28.27	+0.38

mercury (II) and palladium (II), sodium cyanide (1.0 g) was used. The pH was maintained between 7.0 and 7.5 while effecting these separations. Table 2 records the results of one of several determinations.

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF MANGANESE(II) FROM DIVERSE IONS

(Mn taken = 12.55 mg)

Diverse ions	Amount added (mg)	Wt. of the dried complex (mg)	Mn found (mg)	Error (%)
Mg ²⁺	38	109.3	12.53	-0.16
As ³⁺	17	109.4	12.54	-0.08
Sb ³⁺	16	109.4	12.54	-0.08
MoO ₄ ²⁻	24	109.6	12.57	+0.16
WO ₄ ²⁻	26	109.3	12.53	-0.16
Cu ²⁺	17	109.8	12.59	+0.31
Ni ²⁺	15	110.0	12.61	+0.47
Co ²⁺	23	109.7	12.58	+0.23
Zn ²⁺	21	109.6	12.57	+0.16
Cd ²⁺	19	109.8	12.59	+0.31
Hg ²⁺	21	109.7	12.58	+0.23
Pd ²⁺	16	109.9	12.60	+0.38
UO ₂ ²⁺	45	109.8	12.59	+0.31
La ³⁺	50	110.0	12.61	+0.47
Ti ⁴⁺	17	109.3	12.53	-0.16
VO ₃ ⁻	24	109.2	12.52	-0.23
Sn ²⁺	30	109.4	12.54	-0.08
Al ³⁺	35	109.4	12.54	-0.08
Fe ³⁺	25	109.3	12.53	-0.16
Th ⁴⁺	17	109.1	12.51	-0.23

Separation of manganese (II) by adjustment of acidity: A mixture of known quantities of manganese and foreign ions was diluted to 200 ml and its pH was adjusted between 0.5 and 1.0 for titanium (IV), vanadium (V) and tin (II), 4.0 and 4.5 for aluminium (III), iron (III) and thorium (IV) by hydrochloric acid. Titanium¹⁰, vanadium¹¹, tin¹², aluminium⁶, iron⁶ or thorium¹³ was then precipitated with ethanolic solution of the reagent (0.5-1.0 g) as reported. These precipitates were rejected. The filtrate and washings collected together were concentrated to 20 ml and filtered again to remove any organic matter that might have appeared from excess reagent. From the filtrate manganese was determined as described previously. The results are also included in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Properties and composition of the complex: The faint yellow manganese (II)-N-benzoyl-phenylhydroxylamine complex melted with decomposition at 238° ± 1°. The thermolysis curve showed that manganese complex was stable to a temperature of 241° and then the slow decomposition became complete at 500° to furnish probably Mn₂O₃ (weight loss, observed 83.9%, required 83.5%) as the stable ignition product being heated upto 700°. The complex was insoluble in hot (80°) water and sparingly soluble in ethanol, methanol, benzene, acetone, ether, carbontetrachloride and chloroform. The manganese complex was analysed for its carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen content to determine its composition. The composition of the complex corresponds to the formula, Mn(C₁₃H₁₀O₂N)₂ in which manganese to ligand ratio is 1 : 2 (Found : C, 64.95; H, 4.19; N, 5.90%. Calcd. C, 65.14; H, 4.17; N, 5.84%).

Effect of pH: Experimental studies on the determination of manganese (II) in solutions of different pH-values with all other factors similar, showed that the precipitation commenced at pH 5.5 and was complete in the range 6.3-7.8.

Effect of reagent concentration: Precipitation of manganese (II) was carried out at pH 6.5 using different amounts of N-BPHA maintaining all other conditions identical. It was observed that at least 2.5-3 times the theoretical quantity of reagent was necessary for complete precipitation.

Interferences: The precipitation of manganese (II) with N-BPHA was completely inhibited by disodium-EDTA. The anions interfering with the precipitation were fluoride, phosphate, oxalate, citrate and thioglycollate.

Precision and Accuracy: The average error for several determinations of 5-28 mg of manganese (II) in a volume of 200 ml was found to be better than 0.3%.

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